

SPECIAL BRANCHES, STAGES AND VARIOUS TYPES OF TRANSLATION

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SamDChTI 2 kurs magistranti

Abstract: In general there are two types of modern translation - it is oral and written. Oral specializes in working with simultaneous and consecutive translation. It means, the translator immediately translates speech or dialogue. It may be essential during business meetings, speeches of important foreign guests and specialists, etc. The following article gives information about the branches, stages and types of translation.

Keywords: written, oral, interpretation, literal, technical, legal.

The theory of translation is subdivided into general theory, dealing with the general features of translation, regardless of its type, and special branches, concerned with various types of translation, such as the translation of scientific literature. The scientific translation is one of the most important branches because progress depends on the communication of information, while transfer of information from one language to another is bound by many restrictions since each language has its own aspects such as grammatical and lexical properties and cultural aspects which create barriers to readers of those texts Etymologically, 'translate' means to carry across, which is in the case of translation, could mean carrying across a message or a text. Thus, the simplest definition of the translation is rendering the meaning of a text into another language.

When we want to translate any text we are not going to translate grammar, words, style or sounds. What do we translate then? We always translate only one thing – the meaning. But translating meaning literally, the translation will not convey the exact effect of the original text. Hence, in producing the target-language text the translator changes its plan of expression (linguistic form) while its plan of content (meaning)

should remain unchanged. One of the distinctive features of scientific style is preciseness, which is a basic property of a scientific text and should be strictly maintained in translation. A translator must be fully aware of what s/he is translating to render precisely the content of the text. Special attention must be paid to terms. To translate precisely, it is not enough to know an equivalent of the term. It is crucial to know the exact place of the concept, denoted by the term, in relation to other concepts. So, translators in science have to specialize in a particular subject field.

TYPES OF TRANSLATION

Translation includes several features, so its types are divided into the following categories. There is a classification according to different criteria:

Completeness of a translated text,

Purposes of the translation;

Thematic focus.

Usually, translators use a classification based on the subject of the source text provided by the customer. In other words, the specialist considers the object of translation from the point of view of belonging to a certain type of activity.

Technical translation. Characteristics of translation of technical documentation provide accurate interpretation of terms, units of measurement, technical abbreviations and designations on drawings.

Literary or artistic translation. Such work should not only convey the meaning of the text, but also its feature, genre, and style. This is practically the creation of a new literary work. Literary translation includes translation of prose, poems, and songs.

Economic translation. The translator must have specialized knowledge or experience in this field. This is not only knowledge of the terminology of the source language, but also a constant study of the world economy.

Medical translation. Medical translation is one of the most crucial types of translation. To translate a medical document, you must have an excellent command of medical terminology, be able to use specialized reference books and dictionaries.

Legal translation. The major problems of such works are specific design and excellent knowledge of the concepts of the legal system of different states.

STAGES OF TRANSLATION

The correct approach to performance of any translation involves several stages:

Reading and understanding the entire text. Some "experts" do not even read the sentence till the end, just translate it word by word. It adversely affects the quality of the resulting material.

Data analysis, collecting additional information for a deep understanding of the source code are very important stages of translation. It is especially important for the medical translation.

Translation of logically completed parts of the text. It is not recommended to translate the text in violation of the rules of consistency and systemacity.

Proofreading. A special role is played by competent editing of the text in accordance with international standards.

There are a few peculiarities of headlines and ways of their translation

1. For attraction of readers' attention to the main idea of the message in the headlines the articles and personal forms of the auxiliary verb to be are usually dropped.

2. The information about recent events is conveyed using Present Indefinite form. This as if brings an event nearer to the reader and enhances their interest.

3. Future action is often rendered using the Infinitive.

4. Sometimes in the headline the predicate is dropped because it is of less importance in the sentence.

5. To attract readers' attention to the predicate and provoke their interest the subject is dropped if it is of less importance then the predicate.

6. The Genitive case due to its structural compactness is used with inanimate nouns instead of the prepositional construction with of.

7. Often popular nicknames and contracted names are used instead of family names of some politicians, actors, sportsmen etc.

8. For giving some emotional tone to the common lexis headlines often employ neologisms, dialectic words, poetic lexis, or slang.

9. Abbreviations and abridgements are widely used.

10. The figurative elements are often employed

To sum up, we should stress that contrary to the headlines of scientific and technical articles that as a rule give some insight into the main idea of the article's content and thus in a certain way are the “key” to understanding of the text, for the newspaper headlines the situation is different. There are a number of recommendations that help improve the quality of translation both at the stage of the actual translation and at the stage of post-translation editing.

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